

RRING T3.3 RRING Interview Analysis Codebook: Responsible Research and Innovation state-of-the-art global interviews

This codebook will be used to code the interviews conducted globally for the EU Horizon 2020 project: Responsible Research and Innovation Networking Globally (RRING). The structured interviews have been undertaken by RRING partners and additional sub-contractors with clearly defined themes and sections that relate to responsibility in research and innovation practices.

The main objective of the qualitative interviews is to gain a ‘bottom-up’ perspective on RRI that reveals the local practices and policies that are employed to establish research and innovation that is aligned to societal needs and values. This objective requires a focus on perspectives, processes and practices that are employed around the world to ensure that research and innovation is ethical, socially inclusive and addressing public concerns.

The qualitative interviews brought to light the respondents’ personal interpretations, perceptions and understandings of RRI practices. Therefore, the coding is done for the respondents’ social construction of RRI practices and not specifically for ‘factual’ evidence and information. As such, the responses are taken at face value and inferences made accordingly.

This codebook has been prepared inductively in light of the key objective stated above through the qualitative analysis of 30 interviews (list of interviews analysed for preparation of the codebook provided at the end of the document). The coding was done to account for both cross-cutting (i.e. across all the interview questions and all the geographies/domains/etc.) themes as well as context- and question section-specific subject matter. This means that the main themes specified (and numbered as the main headings) in the codebook consist of both the structured interview-based themes (e.g. public engagement, open access and open data, etc) but also cross-cutting inductively identified themes (such as enablers, constraints, conflicts, etc).

This codebook is designed for use by a team of coders who will code the remaining interviews. While the coding is mainly to be done deductively, the coders are expected to flag any critical new codes and reach a satisfactory inter-coder agreement. The descriptions for each code are provided as a source of guidance to better understand what the code means and what areas might be covered within the specified code. The examples are provided to give some additional information on what type of interview text the code may be applied to. In this, greater adherence should be given to the code name, rather than the description. The descriptions are by no means rigid and should be taken as flexible enough to evolve and incorporate additional meanings should the need arise during the coding process.

Some General rules:

The 12 themes represent the highest order of coding, which are further divided into sub-categories and sub-sub-categories. **Coding should be done for the sub-categories and sub-sub-categories** and not directly to the main themes. If in any doubt w.r.t sub-categories, coding should be done for the higher order sub-category, which will retain all codes from child nodes (sub-sub-categories).

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 The terms ‘research’ and ‘innovation’, although distinct, have been combined and all codes made applicable to both for the purpose of simplicity. This is done to ensure that text is captured at the codes for both, without having to account for discrepancies in the responses where there is blurring and distinction might not have been made, or if there exist overlaps.

Since there may be various topics/themes and codes being covered by the respondents in answer to the specific questions, simultaneous coding in the same sentence to cater to multiple codes/themes is completely justified and acceptable. If the coders feel that the same portion of text can be coded to more than one code, it should be coded simultaneously to all relevant codes, so as not to lose important data.

The coders are advised to stick close to the data and not to make too many inferential leaps. This is important because quality of interviews may vary between interviewers and between countries. Many of the interviews have also been translated from a different language into English, with varying qualities, and so necessary caution must be taken to avoid any misconceptions and misinterpretations.

Whilst simultaneous coding is encouraged, especially for Themes 2 and 3, priority should be given to coding for cross-cutting themes, since this is where interesting comparisons can be made and ideas may emerge for the report writing.

Coding can be done for different lengths of text (i.e. word to phrase to sentence to paragraph to page, etc), to best suit the purpose of the code. For example, in themes 2 and 3, since the purpose is to identify the various types of stakeholders and tools used for engagement, the themes can include coding only the names or references to the different stakeholders/tools (i.e. coding a few words and not the entire sentence, especially when a list of stakeholders/tools is being narrated by the respondents which belong to different categories)

Coding should be done even for repetitions. For example, coding should be done every time a stakeholder or tool is mentioned (Themes 2/3), even if it has been mentioned previously.

The code for ‘Organisational norms and practices’ should be used when a) there is lack or uncertainty of norms/practices b) only when other more relevant codes in the specific theme do not apply and c) if the interviewer’s response is more generic and not specific enough to be coded to other more specific codes in the relevant theme/codebook. Otherwise, there is a danger that everything can be coded to this code. Also, be aware of differentiation between codes for negative responses versus positive responses; If positive, there is greater chance for it to be coded to the specific code related to the topic within the wider theme. If negative, it should probably go to ‘organisational norms and practices’ OR ‘Lack or uncertainty of policy’, etc.

Name	Description	Example
1. Public engagement	Reference to public engagement (i.e. involvement/communication/collaboration, etc) of any sort. This can include references to engagement with various stakeholders, between different domains/sectors. (This section will include the provisionally defined section on public engagement in the interview, but will also contain codes for all other text in the transcript that addresses the topic of public engagement)	
Organisational norms and practices	Codes that describe <u>organisational norms and practices</u> (i.e. formal/informal rules and procedures within the organisation) for public engagement <i>OR</i> if the respondent shows any <u>uncertainty</u> about what such norms and practices might be or how they might play a role in public engagement. Rules: This does NOT include govt/supra-institutional level policy (coded below).	I don't think that <i>having an internal regulation is very relevant in our specific case</i> , because we are a SME working on communication. (I04) Our rules within the organisation, we have a written manifesto, since we are an NGO, right, we have a sort of a rulebook... it's a lot easier to understand, it's not like this law terminology, you know how those have to be said, so that's that, I mean, <i>our manifesto sums up our practices and procedures inside the organisation.</i> (SRB02)
Lack or uncertainty of public engagement initiatives/ policy	Any reference to there being a lack of public engagement initiatives or policy (i.e. at the government and other supra-institutional policy levels, beyond the organisation) and reasons provided accordingly <i>OR</i> if the respondent shows any uncertainty about what such existing policies might be or how they might play a role in public engagement. Rules: This will NOT include any organisational policies, which will be coded in the previous code.	There is <i>no such thing I am aware of</i> , and there is nothing preventing us from involving outside groups in our work. (EG10) Well there are very few policies which try to engage people in research or scientific research. I mean, <i>I can't think of</i> , eh,..I can safely say that <i>India doesn't have a national policy for public engagement of science.</i> (IND02)
Motives/benefits of public engagement/ collaboration	Any reference to the motivation behind or the various types of benefits derived from engagement (for any/all stakeholders involved) and collaboration Rules: This can include understanding attitudes, developing trust, increasing awareness, developing credibility and legitimacy, influencing behaviour change, improving R&I outcomes.	Previously, we've tried to argue that it's more important that you have residues in your food. The important distinction now...is <i>trying to understand peoples values</i> rather than necessarily the physical implications of what they say they want. (GB01) There is a lot of interest in making those data available publicly because that would then, I think, it starts to <i>get over the suspicion or lack of trust in us</i> if people can see those data, if people can have the opportunity to analyse the data for themselves and they see that the conclusions that we've drawn from those data are sound, then <i>we can start to win some trust.</i> (GB01) Stakeholders' engagement is key to <i>any type of implementation</i> and we believe that they should be involved from the very beginning. (I04) We have these different types of our multi-faceted approaches to <i>educate the people</i> (ZA01)
Risks/Disadvantages associated with public engagement/ collaboration	Any reference to negative consequences/disadvantages of public engagement (e.g. in terms of fear of bad press or maintaining confidentiality for commercialisation).	Since it is state funded, there is also a fear that more questions will be asked. Where is the money going.(IND02)

Name	Description	Example
	<p>Rules: This will NOT include any references to difficulties faced in engagement or collaboration, which is addressed in themes 12</p>	<p>I don't think I'm particularly involved in public engagement. The projects that I manage are of two kinds, mainly. We have internal projects, which is the research that we're doing just to develop our own products, and that one is highly confidential, so there are no external partners involved, and there is certainly no public engagement about the results because all the results will be then built into our products and commercialized (GB03)</p>
2. Types of stakeholders for engagement/collaboration Listing and describing the various types of stakeholders that the respondent (and their organisation) engages with.		
<p>Government bodies, municipalities and regulatory authorities</p>	<p>Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with any government departments, municipalities or regulatory authorities in terms of R&I. Rules: This will include policy bodies and all official authorities that specify regulations/legislation. It will NOT include other bodies like professional associations or accreditation bodies that will be coded below</p>	<p>We have a direct engagement with the State Government's policy formulation, also with the municipal governments and the Federal Government. (BR03)</p> <p>In other federal units, we also <i>work directly with the health secretary</i> (BR06)</p>
<p>Professional bodies</p>	<p>Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with any professional bodies, such as formal scientific associations/societies/councils or accreditation bodies in terms of R&I. Rules: This will NOT include policy bodies and all official authorities that specify regulations/legislation, which should be coded above.</p>	<p>We <i>cooperate</i> both with the <i>regional innovation technology agency</i> and the in-house public finance company. (I01)</p> <p>The project that I mainly focused on: "Genetically modified foods"... was an individual initiative I started at the xxx, then the xxx team worked together with the formulated group by the Ministry of Environment members of the "National Safety Committee" and with the "Ministry of Agriculture", the "<i>National Agricultural Research Center</i>" (HKJ01)</p>
<p>Research Funding organisations</p>	<p>Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with any research funding organisations in terms of R&I. Rules: This will NOT include research organisations like universities, which will be coded below.</p>	<p>There are <i>two funding agencies</i> within the Egyptian Ministry of communication and information technologies, one is <i>NTRA</i> and the other is the <i>Itak Programme</i> and we are actually <i>coordinating</i>, xxx (EG02)</p> <p>When it comes to <i>European funding</i>, the funding comes with a number of conditions. (GB03)</p>
<p>Scientific community</p>	<p>Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with the scientific community at large. Rules: This can include researchers and academics, educational institutes (universities) or collaborative research institutes like teaching hospitals, etc. This will NOT include research funding organisations which will be coded above</p>	<p>I also work with, I suppose, you could call it, the '<i>scientific community</i>' generally with talks at conferences, lectures at universities...(GB01)</p> <p>...<i>all public universities, all public research centres, some private universities...</i> we are trying to do two things, one is customer-base to increase or attract more young researchers, we are trying to <i>widen the pool of researchers to attract new applicants</i> (EG02)</p>
<p>Specialists/Experts</p>	<p>Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with experts and/or specialists in the specific area of R&I.</p>	<p>Throughout the selection process, we involve <i>specialists from various fields</i>, from people with a more market-oriented approach to technicians (BR05)</p>

Name	Description	Example
Civil society organisations	Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with any civil society organisations such as charities, NGOs, lobby groups or trade unions, trade organisations, etc.	<p>Sometimes we would have discussions <i>with environmental charities</i> for example throughout the world because that can be very influential on political decision-making and then implementation of regulatory decision-making. (GB01)</p> <p>We have got all these other independent entities which are; <i>NGOs, civil organizations that also partner with xxx</i> to take out this information, to make sure that the public is engaged at most cases. (ZA01)</p> <p>Being able to stand up for those interests, <i>the lobbies and that kind of thing also helps</i> beyond the sector where you work; it makes things clear, transparent, stable and applicable to everyone. (ROU02)</p>
Industry and Business	Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with industry and businesses. This can include private companies as well as not-for-profit organisations. Rules: This will NOT include references to any business/companies that are used for marketing/ promotion of R&I, which will be included in the code below.	<p>Another thing is called demand-driven program which is actually- you don't need to be a ministry you could be a <i>private entity, could be a company</i> coming together with a researcher (EG02)</p> <p>We deal mainly with <i>trading companies and waste management service providers and manufacturing companies.</i> (EG10)</p>
Marketing and communication agencies/ Public Relations Industry	Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with marketing and communication agencies. Rules: This can include television networks, radio broadcasting stations, public affairs officers, etc	<p>...someone who works in <i>marketing and communications</i> specifically for technology (SRB02)</p>
Celebrities	Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with celebrities	<p>We try to address cultural behaviour and norms. We also included, in the short movie I mean, a <i>6-min interview with celebrity xxx</i> in xxx about basic science and funded research. (EG02)</p>
Citizens/ general public	Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with the general public, citizens and/or the local community	<p>In the end, in the piloting part, <i>who will apply the project is the community itself</i>; it will also evaluate the results and possible adaptations. In conclusion, we seek to <i>ensure deep involvement of communities at all stages of the process.</i> (BR05)</p> <p>We have a space for <i>dialogue with community leaders</i>, called 'the leaders' meeting', which happens twice a year and brings representatives related to sustainable development in the state. <i>The leaders of each community are summoned, and it is within this collaborative space that we build our research guidelines and project calls.</i> (BR03)</p>
Others	Reference to involvement/influence/interaction with any other stakeholders, not listed above. This can include engagement with primary/secondary educational institutes (e.g. schools and colleges) or religious institutes, etc.	
3. Tools for engagement	Reference to the various techniques/ methods employed for the purpose of engagement. If the emphasis is on the <i>type of stakeholder</i> , coding should be done in Theme 2, whereas if emphasis in on the <i>tools</i> , it will be coded in Theme 3.	

Name	Description	Example
Information-based tools* ¹	Any references to tools that provide information for understanding R&I in the organisation and its norms, procedures and practices related to it. Rules: This will include only one-way communication strategies and NOT two-way communication or engagement.	
- Conferences, symposiums, talks and exhibitions	Any reference to providing information through different presentation-focused events, such as conferences, seminars, lectures, talks, etc.	We present work either through <i>a conference</i> , or a workshop, and all these other different platforms so <i>we are making it easy to share the knowledge</i> and work in terms of what we currently do (ZA01)
- Training and workshops	Any reference to setting up training sessions and/or workshops, where the aim is skills development and capacity building (as opposed to simple information sharing, as in above two codes; conferences and talks)	You will see in our report a number of <i>workshops</i> around 100 to 150 per year, having between 5 and 10,000 people participating in these workshops. (BR03) We conduct <i>training sessions</i> for waste collectors in addition to the local contractors at their areas (EG10)
- Research publications and policy reports	Any reference to providing information through research journals, publication, online research repositories, digital research platforms, and public databases, policy reports, etc	We do also <i>support indexing journals internationally</i> and now we have reached <i>35% increase in the level of indexation for articles and journals</i> , that goes very well with our internationalisation strategy (EG03) One thing we did (without crossing the copy rights law)- all the products, tools and research papers that came out of our funded projects, <i>we have for this a public database including all the names in the papers and the citations data...</i> (EG02)
- Information centres	Any reference to providing information through information centres, such as visitor centres	The <i>xxx Center...</i> where people come there from Monday to Saturday and just go through the <i>xxx care where they explain things</i> such as; what is nuclear energy, what applications are there and what does <i>xxx</i> do within the nuclear science and technology space. (ZA01)
- University open days	Any reference to communication/providing information through university open days.	At the institutional levels, there are some basic kind of engagement (practices) like we will have <i>an open day in a research lab or a university</i> where people can come and visit the lab (IND02)
- Media	Any reference to communication through different media, including print media, broadcast media, and the Internet. Examples include newspapers, brochures, films, radio, TV, websites, blogs and social media Rules: This will NOT include any online research sources such as research papers and online data sets, rather it will include online sources used for communication, such as websites or blogs. Research-based sources should be included in the code 'Research publications and policy reports'	I engaged within my organization with, for example- and they want to <i>make a film</i> . So, a lot of <i>documentaries which are made by this organization</i> , that is <i>xxx-</i> where they <i>try to communicate science to people</i> . They tried to make a <i>radio series</i> ; for example, there was one on climate change. (IND02) ...our <i>website</i> , it is more interactive (EG02) ...there is an attempt at the birth of thematic <i>digital platforms</i> , as can be innovators in cultural heritage, to which we have collaborated with the <i>xxx</i> project (I03)

¹ Based on IAP2's Public Participation Spectrum https://www.iap2.org.au/Tenant/C0000004/00000001/files/IAP2_Public_Participation_Spectrum.pdf

Name	Description	Example
Consultation tools	Any references to tools to obtain public/stakeholder feedback on R&I in the organisation and its norms, procedures and practices related to it. <i>Rules: This will include only one-way communication strategies and NOT two-way communication or engagement.</i>	
- Surveys	Any reference to obtaining feedback through surveys, such as questionnaires and/or interviews, etc	At the symposium, we announce the objectives of the program, and we ask the audience to <i>fill in a questionnaire to give their opinion</i> . We don't make that open on the web. (JPN01)
- Public/citizen consultations	Any reference to obtaining feedback through public consultation, etc	...we invited more than 80 people to participate in the first meeting, which would be a public consultation. (BR03)
- Feasibility studies/working groups	Any reference to obtaining feedback through feasibility studies, and working parties	Sometimes we offer some of these conferences and workshops some <i>free initial feasibility studies</i> and what and how they will benefit from it. (HKJ02) <i>We organize working groups</i> (I03)
Involvement tools	Any references to tools to involve the various relevant stakeholders in the R&I practices in the organisation. This will include two-way communication. <i>Rules: This will NOT include a partnership or role in decision-making.</i>	
- Open public calls and funding initiatives, etc	Any reference to involvement through open-public calls or funding awards/initiatives for R&I	We always try to involve people from outside as much as we can. Now, how do we do it? <i>By sending an open call</i> (SRB02) ...once we have a collaboration set up with academia, we tend to <i>sponsor students and sponsor a lot of the work that they do</i> . (GB03)
- Focus groups and discussions	Any reference to engagement with various stakeholders through mutual communication (such as through focus groups and discussion tables, etc). <i>Rules: This will not include any one-way information/knowledge sharing, as in conferences, talks, etc, which will be coded above.</i>	...organized meeting and <i>focus groups</i> with all the subjects participating in these measures for establishing relational dynamics. (I01) we involved housewives, people from the market and other types of people where we asked them different questions concerning waste from their perspectives <i>through focus groups</i> . (HKJ04)
- Competitions and awards	Any reference to involvement of relevant stakeholders through public competitions and awards	There's something called <i>xxx Awards</i> that we do towards the end of the year; <i>award citizens who have played an important role; award xxx xxx who have played an important role</i> in tending to the city. All these are tools that we use in order to uh, you know, steer people (IND04)
- Tie-ups with local schools	Any reference to involvement of school students in R&I initiatives through associations with local schools.	Scientific societies have <i>tie ups, you know, with some schools or colleges</i> where scientists go and talk about their science (IND01) When it comes to state schools, throughout our contract, we have to <i>qualify some good technicians down there</i> , and that depends on the project. (HKJ02)

Name	Description	Example
Collaboration tools	Any references to tools to develop partnerships with various relevant stakeholders for R&I. Rules: This will include a two-way communication and/or engagement and NOT include any one-way communication tools	
- Social networks	Any reference to engagement/collaboration through social networks (personal contacts, etc)	We [established] <i>a face to face connection</i> and then we see what we'd like to work on together and we find the topic and <i>they each bring their friends. I bring my friends.</i> (IL02)
- University-based start-ups	Any reference to collaboration between research institutes and industry/businesses through university-based entrepreneurial activities.	<i>It's a start-up within academia.</i> So, we have been developing a software commercialized through the xxx TRDF [research and development xxx] (IL04)
- Applied research laboratories	Any reference to collaboration between research institutes and industry/businesses through applied research laboratories.	...we suggested that a team should be formed, and we designate an investment to <i>set up an applied research laboratory</i> (BR05)
- R&I matchmaking	Any reference to identifying key stakeholders and facilitating connections between different types of stakeholders. Rules: This can include any references to an intermediary role to bring about engagement of various stakeholders.	We are what I would call an ' <i>orchestrator</i> '. <i>We identify field partners</i> , with access and cooperatives, who help in selecting actors with an understanding of the problems, <i>then connect these actors with spaces of science and technology</i> . As for financing, it can happen in many ways... <i>we bridge the lender with the communities</i> (BR05) xxx has already been described as a <i>catalyst</i> , <i>as we put people in touch</i> to bring solutions that meet our target audience (BR03)
Empowerment tools	Any references to tools to place decision-making in the hands of various relevant stakeholders for R&I. Rules: Empowerment here is not restricted to giving new opportunities to new voices only, but also for promoting existing vested interests.	
- Participatory management/ approaches	Any reference to the use of participatory management techniques. Participation refers to the active involvement and empowerment of members of a group, such as employees of a company or citizens of a community, to participate in organisational decision making.	The main innovation is the social technology of <i>participative management of development processes with traditional communities, indigenous populations, and populations of high urban vulnerability</i> , to which we have been working in recent year (BR03)
- Campaigning/ Lobbying	Any reference to engagement through campaigning/lobbying, i.e. any reference to attempts to persuade/influence the actions, policies, or decisions of officials, most often legislators or members of regulatory agencies to support a particular policy or campaign. This can include demonstration, petitions, vigils, etc.	xxx xxx <i>deals with lobbying</i> (I03)

Name	Description	Example
- Open innovation approach- the quadruple-helix stakeholder model	Any reference to the explicit use of the specific framework of the Quadruple-helix stakeholder model, which involves engagement with public institutions, private organizations, academia and citizens	Mainly, <i>our activities are designed to involve quadruple-helix stakeholders in co-creation and engagement activity.</i> (I04) The implementation of these public funding programs follows <i>the open innovation approach</i> and, in particular, <i>application of the quadruple helix methodology.</i> (I01)
Other	Reference to any other <u>tools for engagement</u> not identified in the listed code categories.	
4. Open access and open data Reference to open access and open data (This section will include the provisionally defined section on open access in the interview, but will also contain codes for all other text in the transcript that addresses the topic of open access)		
Levels and limits of open access	Any reference to limits on open access or different rules, procedures or criteria for open access/data needed at different levels of the organisation (or beyond). Rules: This can include any references to sharing only particular forms of data (e.g. sharing results and outcomes, not data or vice versa; sharing policy-driven research, not market-driven research, sharing with key stakeholders and not the general public, etc) This should also be distinguished from risks/disadvantages of open access/data, which are concerned with negative consequences, while this includes the limits that need to be applied in certain specific instances to open access/data.	A lot of discussions of whether it will be done...will be ...a reputation or advantages of doing this against the commercial disadvantages of doing that. <i>This kind of discussion would probably be at the project level rather than at the company level.</i> It would make a decision based on the value for a particular project, not necessarily across the huge portfolio of projects. (GB01) If in the context of some projects, there is a proprietary business approach then, <i>I do not think there are particular problems to share research data in an open way, I believe that on the results it is necessary to decide which direction to follow</i> (open or proprietary approach). (I03) Not that there is a law, but that we know of complementarity between institutions, <i>we share the information based on a strategic bias, and that benefits both parties. So, data sharing happens in a natural and strategic way for institutions that need input from one another to develop activities</i> and gather information or carry out activities in the reserves (BR03)
Data protection	Any reference to data protection being undertaken or the need to ensure the protection of data. Rules: This code will include any reference to data and its protection, whereas ‘protection of rights’ in Ethics will cover protection of other stakeholder rights, such as consent, confidentiality, etc.	There is another type of information that we cannot give, because <i>we have a law for the protection of private personal data</i> (ROU02) There are regulations that must be respected <i>starting from the GDPR</i> which protects some aspects of the research activities of those who produce the results. (I01)
Data accessibility	Any reference to what is needed/required to make data truly and realistically accessible and meaningful when it is labelled as ‘open access/data’. Any reference to the implication that data can be ‘open access’ but not accessible <i>per se</i> .	There are two levels of problems: first of all, in most cases <i>these results are not accessible because they are simply not published</i> , so we find out in several cases that a lot of projects have the website that is closed the day after the end of the project or <i>the results are hidden in big deliverables and it is not easy to find these results</i> , and then, <i>even if they are accessible it is not easy to find them</i> . Therefore, <i>the main problem is not to make the data open but make them accessible and easily findable by the potential users.</i> (I04)

Name	Description	Example
Organisational norms and practices	Codes that describe <u>organisational norms and practices</u> (i.e. formal/informal rules and procedures within the organisation) for open access <i>OR</i> if the respondent shows any <u>uncertainty</u> about what such norms and practices might be or how they might play a role in open access/data. Rules: This does NOT include any discussion on govt/supra-institutional policy (coded below).	<p>I don't think there is a problem with that, it is just not a routine thing, at xxx we need to collect proper consents, proper preapprovals , if we have this (it is in our plan) we haven't implement that yet but if we do I don't think there is a legal problem that's stops it. (EG02)</p> <p><i>I did not realize for a long time what was open source because in the model of education in our schooling system, at least for my generation, and I think it's a mentality ... things are simply assumed. I did not even know what an open source was, and did not realise it until recently, I have to admit. (SRB04)</i></p>
Lack or uncertainty of policy	Coding for any reference to respondent's uncertainty about govt/institutional policy or a lack of govt/institutional policy for open access and open data (beyond the organisation). Rules: This does NOT include any discussion on organisational norms and practices (both formal and informal) (coded above).	<p><i>We don't have institutional policy for open access or open data at xxx, no we haven't done that, not yet. (EG02)</i></p> <p><i>There is no such regulation for that, but we are going to make one, since, of course, we support open access. (EG03)</i></p>
Risks/Disadvantages associated with open data/access	Any reference to the negative consequences/disadvantages of having data open access (e.g. in terms of IP rights, patents, commercially sensitive data, competitive advantage, data distortion, financial concerns, data overload, misuse/shortcomings or negative perceptions attached to open-access journals, etc).	<p>There's an interesting trade off to be made here; you could see advantages in making your data available but <i>you can also see disadvantages as well</i> and similar arguments on the commercial side; not only about safety of data but about how well the product works, that kind of thing. <i>It might be commercially very sensitive, so there were always going to be pros and cons with open data. (GB01)</i></p> <p>The problems come in the following thing: Once you create your data, what you want to do is to process it and make it into publications or packages that you could put your name on, you get a reputation for a new (publication), if you simply pass it out, then <i>somebody else can do that before you get around to doing it. (IL01)</i></p> <p>Most scientists have the desire to <i>see their research monetized. (BR05)</i></p> <p><i>There are problems with open access also in the sense that you can get published by paying and that has also given rise to a lot of so-called predatory journals... Because of this system, because of the misuse or you know, people are trying to misuse that system. Both publishers as well as researchers. So that is a huge issue. And one has to, of course, open access is welcome, but there are problems with that, and one has to be careful. (IND02)</i></p>
Motives/ Benefits of open access and data	Any reference to benefits of open access, such as influencing public opinion, furthering research and policy, improved visibility, allowing corrective measures, etc.	<p>I also deal with the context of the social challenges, where the research product is very important to be open because it must be able to <i>actively influence public opinion on some important issues. (I03)</i></p> <p>It is important that these data should be open in general but also to us, in order to <i>allow corrective measures and then to improve (I03)</i></p> <p>The motive for journals to go open access is <i>for the visibility (EG03)</i></p>

Name	Description	Example
Diversity and inclusion	Reference to best practices for diversity and inclusion (This section will include the provisionally defined section on diversity and inclusion in the interview, but will also contain codes for all other text in the transcript that addresses the topic of diversity and inclusion)	
Contextual understanding of diversity and inclusion- societal and cultural norms	Any reference to the need for a context-based understanding of diversity and inclusion, since diversity can mean different things in different contexts. It can also include any reference to societal norms, cultures and attitudes related to diversity and inclusion that exist in the specific society and affect diversity and inclusion practices Rules: This will NOT include organisational practices and norms regarding diversity and inclusion, which should be coded below in the relevant section.	<p>When people from abroad look at us, they don't understand what diversity actually is and what diversity means here; that it means Albanians, Vlachs, Muslims, Catholics, and whatnot, all those different ethnic and religious minorities. Here, <i>it's not the race that's at play, but more the ethnic, national, religious choices, and so forth</i> (SRB02)</p> <p>The trajectory of the amount of work research is doing works very fine <i>until you get to 30 or 35, get married and have children</i>. My son has twins. And he's tried to work as a full time [medical] doctor and he's trying to do his PhD. And he looks after the twins some of the time, but <i>his wife looks after the twins</i>. The department I was in [University of] xxx until relatively recently, there was <i>not a single married woman or a single woman who had children</i> (IL01)</p> <p>However, regarding the kind of work itself and the fieldwork, <i>it must be done by men. It is more like a norm to deal with men in this field</i>; however, there are some women doing the job of sorting the waste. (EG10)</p>
Organisational norms and practices	Codes that describe <u>organisational norms, policies and practices</u> (i.e. formal/informal rules and procedures within the organisation or specific models or frameworks used) for diversity and inclusion <i>OR</i> if the respondent shows any <u>uncertainty</u> about what such norms and practices might be or how they might play a role in diversity and inclusion. Rules: This can include both explicit protocol (official institutional norms, codes, rules or guidelines) and implicit norms and values. If any norms/practices are mentioned regarding specific aspects of diversity and inclusion, they should be coded to the relevant codes below. This will NOT include any govt/supra-institutional policies, which will be coded in the relevant code below.	<p><i>In xxx, are their institution policies, which sort of acknowledge this diversity or sort of promote it?</i></p> <p>Speaker 2: <i>I don't think I'll be able to answer that</i>. I am not engaged a great deal with rest of xxx. That's there. But as far as I know, <i>there are no specific policies</i>. They follow the government norms and policies. (IND02)</p>
Gender/Sexual diversity	Any references to gender/sexual diversity and inclusion in R&I/workplace. This can include references to the need or methods employed for improving gender/sexual equality, inclusion/support for LGBT, reducing the gender gap (e.g. a gap in pay, recruitment, promotion, participation, scientific/research domains, etc.) and providing relevant support structure.	<p>We may have had some <i>restrictions in recruitment process where some vacancies or posts were oriented to males</i>, especially in the higher or senior managerial positions, but <i>I see now this has changed</i>. (EG03)</p> <p>Even during the xxx industry association, we get men and women who can be business suppliers, you know suppliers within the xxx industry are from companies which are male dominated, <i>but we also have female</i>. (ZA01)</p>

Name	Description	Example
	<p>Rules: Any negative responses to gender/sexual diversity will be included in the code ‘Discrimination and lack of diversity’.</p>	<p>We always specifically <i>try to engage more female members, female students, trying to create that sort of interest in the nuclear industry</i> (ZA01)</p> <p>The goal was 50% of participants in the diagnosis [to be women]. So, out of the 60 interviews, <i>the goal was to have half of those interviews with women.</i> (BR05)</p> <p>Laws are needed not to promote the minority in the company, but rather to <i>overcome the problems that are related to them.</i> For instance, if a lady has to deal with the family because there are no schools or no support, this means that she has to do her work and she has to take care of the family and also of the elderly people. Consequently, she may not be so productive. It could be <i>a net of supports provided by the government</i> that can help her in that sense. It is not a question of saying “50% should go to the ladies” but it is a question to say “<i>we need to enable these people to work properly through a net of help</i> that can put them in the same position as the other players (of the men). (I04)</p>
Ethnic and religious diversity	<p>Reference to ethnic and religious diversity in R&I/ workplace. This will include references to racial and religious diversity, inclusion of ethnic/religious minority groups, etc</p> <p>Rules: This will NOT include any references to gender minorities, which will be included in the code above. It will also NOT include any reference to the inclusion of specific nationalities, which will be included in the code below. Any negative responses to ethnic/religious diversity will be included in the code ‘Discrimination and lack of diversity’.</p>	<p>Even in our early days in the institution, our <i>Christian fellow colleagues</i> were really helpful back then and we can't deny their help even now (HKJ02)</p> <p>In terms of public policy, <i>we have quotas for racial diversity</i> (BR05)</p>
Country-based representation	<p>Any reference to or the need for diversity and inclusion in R&I/ workplace in terms of representation of different countries and nationalities</p> <p>Rules: This code will refer to improving diversity and inclusion in R&I through ensuring different countries and nationalities are represented and that the concepts/ideas/approaches from different countries should be a part of (R)RI. Any negative responses to country-based diversity will be included in the code ‘Discrimination and lack of diversity’.</p>	<p>There is also <i>a need to balance US versus European researchers.</i> I see it because I'm in both communities. I want to make a point to think that is important. <i>There are not enough opportunities to bridge the EU and the US.</i> (IL02)</p>
Disability	<p>Any reference to how disability is addressed in organisational norms and practices.</p> <p>Rules: Any negative responses to disability will be included in the code ‘Discrimination and lack of diversity’.</p>	<p>As an institution, we have to hire a number of disabled people. (JPN01)</p>

Name	Description	Example
	<p>Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/ workplace in terms of qualification or affiliation with a specific educational institute.</p> <p>Rules: Any negative responses to academic diversity will be included in the code 'Discrimination and lack of diversity'.</p>	<p>We also have another project related to innovative ideas. Previously, the edicts were aimed <i>only at researchers with doctorates and postdocs</i>, now for the first time, <i>any researcher from xxx, can submit a project</i>. And for our part, we are committed to evaluate the curriculum and only evaluate the ideas. (BR06)</p> <p><i>We even care about academic diversity, we don't want people that have all gone to the same university, or to the same handful of universities, because that just means that we are just getting clones.</i> (GB03)</p>
Age diversity	<p>Any reference to diversity and inclusion in terms of age group in R&I/ workplace.</p> <p>Any negative responses to age diversity will be included in the code 'Discrimination and lack of diversity'.</p>	<p>There is some affirmative actions for this not for the gender but for <i>age groups</i>, we have in xxx programs to <i>support younger researchers</i>, so we mandate that the PI and the co PI to be less than 40 years old, and half the team should be less than 30 years ((EG02)</p>
Socio-economic diversity and inclusion	<p>Any reference to diversity and inclusion in R&I/ workplace in terms of different socio-economic groups and classes in society</p> <p>Rules: Any negative responses to socio-economic diversity will be included in the code 'Discrimination and lack of diversity'.</p>	<p>As a geographic question of where we are located, surrounded by several communities of low income. Of course, it is about health, but above all, <i>it also involves this social dimension of the discussion of inequality in the country.</i> (BR06)</p> <p>We make sure it is <i>inclusive of, you know, people who are the lowest in the scale.</i> (IND04)</p>
Motives/ Benefits of diversity and inclusion	<p>Any reference to the motives for and benefits of diversity and inclusion, e.g. helps in getting a more comprehensive understanding or basis for R&I.</p>	<p>We are encouraging them to use the "GBA Plus", because it <i>makes them think in a wider perspective.</i> (HKJ04)</p> <p>I think it is highly relevant because... if you're only talking to a small perhaps unrepresentative side of society, <i>you're not going to get the full picture</i> so I think that it is a really important part of doing by <i>having lots of types of people involved in your organization.</i> (GB01)</p>
Risks/Disadvantages associated with diversity and inclusion	<p>Any reference to the negative consequences/disadvantages of having diversity and inclusion (e.g. in terms of sacrificing research quality to meet diversity objectives).</p>	<p>We have already thought of establishing a given criteria, for example, at least one of the winners should be female, but then again <i>there are also ethical questions to search for the best solution for the community.</i> Ultimately, for the community, no matter who made the solution, what matters is that it is the best solution. So, <i>I also cannot choose a solution that may not be the most appropriate to reach a goal, when in the end I would be affecting the final beneficiary.</i> (BR05)</p>
Discrimination and lack of diversity	<p>Reference to lack of any diversity and inclusion within the organisation that leads to discrimination. This can include references to lack of ethnic or age diversity, lack of female inclusion, lack of acknowledgement of disability, etc. This can include references to specific <u>organisational norms and practices that lead to a lack of diversity and inclusion.</u></p> <p>Rules: It will NOT include any reference to lack or uncertainty of govt/institutional policy, which is included in the code below.</p>	<p><i>Regarding ethnicities, I think there is still some concerns</i>, but they are making a lot of efforts to fix that, but this is my impression. Unfortunately, at the public institutions, <i>we still consider seniority in term of long residence in one place rather than who is the best fit for any position</i>, which can destroy any good work we are doing. (EG03)</p> <p>I also aim at the proportion of women in the jurors' body, and also as proponents, i.e. scientists and inventors. However, <i>save the female participation in the diagnostic phase, in the other stages I have great difficulty in meeting the goals</i>, it is still a great challenge (BR05)</p>

Name	Description	Example
		<p>We still have some <i>norms affecting selection of candidates like considering religion and sometime wide types of favouritism exist.</i> (EG03)</p> <p><i>There have been recent incidents of university entrance being biased towards males... I don't know if I should say this since I just started work here...but I haven't heard anything related to gender in the first training sessions.</i>(JPN01)</p>
Lack or uncertainty of policy	<p>Coding for any reference to respondent's uncertainty about govt/supra-institutional policy or a lack of govt/supra-institutional policy regarding diversity and inclusion (beyond the organisation).</p> <p>Rules: This does NOT include any discussion on organisational norms and practices, which will be coded for each of the types of diversity and inclusion specified in the codes above.</p>	<p>This is an issue that has <i>not yet entered consistently on the funding providers' agenda...We do not have for the participation of women in these sectors, so I do not know to what extent public policy influences this issue or not.</i> (BR05)</p> <p><i>We don't have such institutional policies or regulations</i> (EG03)</p>
Discrimination: a non-issue	<p>Any reference to the respondents' opinion of diversity and inclusion never being an issue in their institute/organisation or any indication that discrimination or inequality does not exist.</p>	<p>So far, this has not been actually a conscious error. It is like <i>we never paid attention to it.</i> So We have people working and we make sure that everybody is comfortable so in that way, there has not been a very conscious effort that these kinds of people we will bring But when we are working with people and finding out people, <i>we are never looking at the person's gender and all these things doesn't form part of their evaluation, the balance is no different.</i> (IND01)</p> <p>In the innovation field, it is possible to observe noteworthy participation also by female entrepreneurs. There are many companies led by women in the technological field, so <i>we have no problems from this point of view. There are no gender or social inequalities.</i> (I01)</p>
6. Ethics	<p>Reference to best practices for following and implementing ethical standards (This section will include the provisionally defined section on ethics in the interview, but will also contain codes for all other text in the transcript that addresses the topic of ethics)</p>	
<p>Positioning ethics- where does the responsibility lie?</p> <p>- Disidentification with ethical responsibility</p>	<p>Reference to where the ethical responsibilities lie and who defines them (within the organisation or beyond). This can be in terms of rules/standards within the organisation or beyond, national vs international level policies, etc.</p> <p>Codes that describe normative perceptions regarding ethics within specific disciplines or fields, such as environmental research, which indicate a disidentification with ethical responsibility or lack of relevance of ethics in some way</p>	<p>I suppose ethics perhaps comes a little bit before to where we get involved...what we are often looking at is <i>regulation being the result of ethical discussions that have happened before we're getting involved</i> rather than us been told to have discussions about ethics with people. (GB01)</p> <p>If you were doing <i>environmental research</i>, I can <i>barely think of any situation in which you would think what you were doing was causing concerns for society.</i> (IL01)</p> <p>These are the only times I can think of ever being involved in anything that might have been detrimental to society. Otherwise, <i>we like to think we do the opposite.</i> (IL01)</p>
- Personal responsibility and morality	<p>Any reference to a sense of personal responsibility and morality as a guide for ethics in the workplace.</p>	<p>I do not recognize any institutional, no institutional premise, no politics...on the contrary, I solely and responsibly claim that the only model that takes us into a</p>

Name	Description	Example
	<p>Rules: This code refers to the respondents' sense of a personal moral code, as opposed to any institutional norms/ policies and is about positioning ethics within their own sense of moral obligation. It highlights the difference between when they have had to do something to follow certain protocols versus desire to do something because it is what they believe is the right thing to do.</p>	<p>maximally fair and correct high ethical relationship... is a <i>personal ethical framework</i> that man gets from his education, upbringing or home. (SRB04)</p>
Organisational norms and practices	<p>Codes that describe <u>organisational norms and practices</u> (i.e. formal/informal rules and procedures within the organisation) for ethics <i>OR</i> if the respondent shows any <u>uncertainty</u> about what such norms and practices might be or how they might play a role in ethics.</p> <p>Rules: This can include both explicit protocol (official institutional norms, codes, rules or guidelines) and implicit norms and values. It will NOT include any reference to lack or uncertainty of govt/institutional policy, which is included in the relevant code below.</p>	<p>There are behavioural codes that are defined by xxx to which we respect as a system federation and then as a system association. There is a checking mechanism which, in the event that a possible problems arises, <i>activates internal verification systems...</i> when the behaviour is not in line with the ethical code of the confederation, limiting the action of the subjects possibly involved, up to their expulsion. (I03)</p> <p>We have trained researchers who are actually <i>explaining to them the benefits and concerns and actually ethical aspects of this project.</i> (IND01)</p> <p>There are, what I would say, <i>broadly accepted, you know, norms. But there's no set ethical standard,</i> for example, when you write about, say, things involving women and children. (IND02)</p> <p>In effect, university was saying <i>academics can do anything.</i> There is almost nothing that academics can do that will cause the university to remove them, including sexual harassment.</p> <p>S: <i>So, you are saying, better and for worse, academics have a lot of latitude?</i> Well, <i>that's the whole point of academia, the whole point is, is that you do not get told what to do</i> (IL01)</p>
Safety and security	Any references to safety and security as an important ethical issue in R&I	Whatever we do in the nuclear technologies, <i>safety is paramount; safety of the public, safety of the environment.</i> (ZA01)
Justice and fair dealing	Any references to justice and fair dealing as an important ethical issue in R&I	It's enough for me in my own personal, moral framework to know that I work maximally <i>fair and correct.</i> (SRB04)
Quality assurance and testing	<p>Any references to quality assurance and quality control measures taken, i.e. ensuring the maintenance of a desired level of quality and standard in a service or product in R&I.</p> <p>Rules: This can include any reference to R&I testing and piloting.</p>	The software development is done in an agile way, but we do ensure that every releasee is <i>rigorously tested.</i> We have two environments to test it, a development environment, and a "sandbox" to test it. (IL04)

Name	Description	Example
 Transparency	Any references to ensuring accessibility, honesty, visibility and openness of organisational operations, actions and outcomes as an important ethical issue. Rules: This will NOT include any references to accountability which includes the capacity to sanction or compensate, which will be coded below.	the reports we disclose, which are a way to account for partners, we try to put figures and graphs in an extremely visual way, keeping in mind <i>transparency for every financial investment and donation from partners</i> . (BR03) As I told you, in our field, we <i>have a strong issue with transparency</i> , that's why we choose to have this as our main value proposition in the market. (EG10)
Accountability	Any reference to the need for liability and answerability of organisational operations, actions and outcomes as an important ethical issue. This will include the capacity to sanction or compensate.	...Sort of Good Laboratory Practices and various regulations that mean <i>you could be inspected or the accompany that is producing some of that data can be inspected</i> adds a strong incentive to behave honestly. (GB01) Bulk of research in India is state funded... private money is very little. So, <i>in some sense there needs to be accountability also</i> . So, the job of a journalist or a science communicator is to identify that and connect it. (IND02) Almost all our money comes from taxpayers, but <i>they have very little accountability from us</i> (JPN02)
Lack or uncertainty of ethical standards/policy	Coding for any reference to respondent's uncertainty about govt/institutional policy or a lack of govt/institutional policy regarding ethics (beyond the organisation). Rules: This does NOT include any discussion on organisational norms and practices, which will be coded above in the relevant code.	What government or institutional policies and regulations affect how you address ethics in your work? <i>Nothing that I am aware of.</i> (EG10) <i>Well no, because I think that in Serbia, I mean that's ridiculous.</i> I mean really. (SRB02)
Protection of rights	Any reference to protecting the rights of all stakeholders by ensuring consent, confidentiality, ownership and intellectual rights, preventing copyright infringement, plagiarism and fraud, avoiding conflict of interest, protection from liabilities, etc	<i>But from the moment we share the information, we ask the partner to tell us where it will be published, and if the sources can be shared.</i> (BR03) <i>We seek to protect the intellectual property generated in these processes</i> (BR05) <i>You can start the research with the participants again following their human ethics practice, getting the informed consent and clarity and, uh, anonymity and all those things. These things are provided to them before they participate.</i> (IND01) <i>Sometimes we do plagiarism checks, but we rely on ethical committees in universities and research centres specially in the medical</i> (EG02) <i>IP is the thing that we produce, and it is very important for us to protect it... before we even start talking to a consortium, before we even start talking to academia, we have to obtain non-disclosure agreements from everyone involved, and we can only talk about IP and ideas and concepts that have already been protected in some way, normally with patents.</i> (GB03)

7. Meeting societal needs Reference to any specific benefits to society explicitly mentioned

Name	Description	Example
(This section will include the provisionally defined section on meeting societal needs in the interview, but will also contain codes for all other text in the transcript that addresses the topic of societal needs)		
Demand-driven research and innovation	Reference to setting the goal/agenda for R&I based on providing specific solutions to specific problems existing in the society. Rules: This can include references to meeting societal needs through focus on UN SDGs, local development, developing the right types of products that are needed on ground, etc.	When we determine a participatory approach, we automatically <i>solve problems that are listed by the community...</i> we had an innovation with the xxx Council and a private company of electric power systems some time ago, in which the idea was to build a research call where we brought a multi-stakeholder participatory bias. Then, <i>considering issues raised by the community, the project sought to answer these questions</i> by associating scientific points from both the UK and the Amazon participants. (BR03) At the most basic level you talk to the people who are going to be your customers to make sure that you are <i>developing the right kind of product.</i> (GB01)
- Targeting critical societal challenges	Any reference to <u>existing or imminent</u> critical challenges that R&I focuses on (can be around the UN SDGs). This can include issues of health and wellbeing, waste management, access to resources and infrastructure, environmental protection, etc.	We have focus more on <i>energy, water or agriculture sectors, those are within the societal challenge for Egypt.</i> (EG03)
- Benefiting specific groups	Any reference to benefiting specific groups and segments of the society through R&I, e.g. R&D in less-known vulnerability areas, or the middle or developing economies, or minorities, etc.	... trying to aim at creating solutions for diagnostics, which is affordable and reliable. And, in this case we are hoping that <i>it will be hugely beneficial for people with a minimum of resources.</i> (IND01) There's quite a focus on, for us, <i>on supporting people who are struggling to pay their energy bills</i> , because they're on lower incomes. So, we sort of have additional... We deliver services that <i>provide additional support for low-income households.</i> (GB08)
- Furthering research/ Developing policy/standards	Any reference to local policy development or support in development of regulations/standards.	In many ways what we're doing, if you talk about research, it <i>influences the policy and brings policy change</i> , be it the Delhi bylaws be it the Delhi action plan on Waste that we worked on. Be it, Bihar strategy on a solid waste management based on our work in xxx be it the bylaws in xxx that, that soon to be framed, which we had drafted and the implementation work that has happened there, which <i>led to those bylaws.</i> (IND04)
Organisational norms and practices	Codes that describe <u>organisational norms, policies and practices</u> (i.e. formal/informal rules and procedures within the organisation or specific models or frameworks used) for meeting societal needs <i>OR</i> if the respondent shows any <u>uncertainty</u> about what such norms and practices might be or how they might play a role in meeting societal needs. Rules: This can include both explicit protocol (official institutional norms, codes, rules or guidelines) and implicit norms and values.	We are the only example of a <i>circular economy</i> in the region and in the Balkans (SRB05) It has a strategic dimension issue and has unique health systems that have to give to its population in the developing country all the inputs. How do you guarantee this within one business model; <i>what we call social business, we have to have a commitment to the sustainability of activities, but at the same time, it is our greatest goal to meet SUS (Unified Health System) and their demands.</i> (BR06)

Name	Description	Example
Lack of consideration of societal benefits	Coding for any reference to a lack of consideration of societal benefits in the R&I framework of the organisation/institution	<i>Our work is quite removed from the end user. We are not... So, we provide... We design chips, for example, that we're aiming to make them faster, to make them low cost, to make them low energy using, and that sort of thing, but that's kind of a driver of the industry rather than society. (GB03)</i>
Lack or uncertainty of policy for meeting societal needs	Coding for any reference to respondent's uncertainty about govt/supra-institutional policy or a lack of govt/supra-institutional policy regarding meeting societal challenges/needs (beyond the organisation). Rules: This does NOT include any discussion on organisational norms and practices, which will be coded above in the relevant code.	
8. Anticipation Reference to any form of future-oriented thinking and anticipation for R&I (This section will include the provisionally defined section on anticipation in the interview, but will also contain codes for all other text in the transcript that addresses the topic of future implications and future-oriented decision-making)		
Future societal needs/challenges	Any reference to consideration of future societal challenges or needs in R&I practices Rule: This does not include any references to meeting existing needs (covered in the last theme, rather thinking about what future needs might occur and designing R&I approaches accordingly.	This allows us to <i>refine the coherence between our study and research initiatives and the growing needs of public opinion</i> which is our market. (I03) Well I would like to cite an Indian chief that says that we practically borrowed our country from our descendants... people that work in environmental protection understand this very well. On one hand, they have the knowledge and skills, on the other, they simply see that <i>today's work, today's consequences will be felt in the future, no matter how we engage with it</i> (SRB07)
Environmental sustainability	Any reference to future implications of research and innovation with regards to sustainability, environmental protection, climate change, etc. This can include future-oriented consideration of environmental sustainability both in terms of R&I processes and outcomes.	The work that we do is <i>to improve the current generation with the consideration of the future generations</i> but also finding proper solutions that came from through us. We also don't want to have something that will become a burden for the future generation. <i>The aim is to solve issues of current, also looking into the future to see how that will benefit those that are coming in the future.</i> (ZA01) <i>The project plans take sustainability in the design process.</i> (HKJ04)
Responsive approach	Any reference to undertaking research and innovation that is reactive and responsive to evaluation processes and public/societal needs and demand. This can include adaptation to changes or using a trial and error approach, etc. Rules: This code is more concerned with the degree of flexibility of the R&I process and outcomes in their <u>ability</u> to change and account for any future needs, and NOT about evaluation <i>per se</i> , which should be coded above.	...trying to understand <i>how is that going to affect our ability to market it to get societal acceptance for it, is it going to affect how the things are regulated? How is it perhaps how would negative, or positive reactions change the market?</i> (GB01) You cannot rely on stable and long-term legislation, everything can happen in every moment and so you try but finally, <i>it is more a question of adapting to the continuous change in the law.</i> (I04)
Organisational norms and practices	Codes that describe <u>organisational norms, policies and practices</u> (i.e. formal/informal rules and procedures within	<i>We are really guided by a normal, how to say, widely accepted, highly ethical norm in relation to the elemental human rights. And elemental rights, human rights are nutrition, freedom, air, water and well-being. I hold on to it.</i> (SRB04)

Name	Description	Example
	<p>the organisation) for anticipation/future-implications of work OR if the respondent shows any <u>uncertainty</u> about what such norms and practices might be or how they might play a role in anticipation/future-implications. It will NOT include any reference to lack or uncertainty of govt/institutional policy, which is included in the code below.</p>	<p><i>What policies and norms... As of now, no. Uh, I'm not sure that exists any policies that actually evaluates implication in that long term....the performance evaluation that is set by xxx for the professor and Associate Professor's evaluation, those are the things that basically, uh, to some extent, drive people to make contribution and things like that.</i>(IND01)</p>
<p>Lack or uncertainty of anticipation policy and framework</p>	<p>Coding for any reference to respondent's uncertainty about govt/supra-institutional policy or a lack of govt/supra-institutional policy regarding anticipation (beyond the organisation). Rules: This does NOT include any discussion on organisational norms and practices, which will be included in the code above.</p>	<p>No, not really, there are (no) particular regulation or policy affecting how we consider future implications (EG03)</p>

Cross-cutting Themes

9. Enablers **Factors that enable engagement for RRI**
 (This section will include references to any enablers of RRI from the entire interview text and so will include high-level codes that cut across all or most of the RRI themes on which the interview questions are bases)

<p>Accounting for local contexts</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Importance of customisation 	<p>Any reference to the role of context in determining and/or undertaking RRI practices. See sub-categories below</p> <p>Any reference to the importance of a custom-tailored approach for R&I in all/varying aspects of responsibility (e.g. communication and engagement, ethics, etc)</p>	<p>Every audience is different, you know. So, what I communicate to one audience need not be the same thing. <i>It has to be tailor made.</i> Then only people will be able to understand science or research or its roots and see the relevance of it to their own life (IND02)</p> <p>I cannot generalize because <i>each case is different.</i> In the issue of access to water, for example, we asked about inputs and risks for the population, however, in the case of agriculture and machinery, these the same questions would no longer make sense, so we asked about physical damage. So really, <i>each case is a different approach.</i> (BR05)</p> <p><i>It depends on the topic we want to discuss and also it depends on the level (if we are working at the regional local level, the national level, or the international level).</i> It is absolutely important to identify what is the main goal and outcome that you want to achieve with your activities. Goal and outcome are the two criteria that are driving the selection and the involvement of participants (I04)</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Contextualising technology and innovation 	<p>Any reference to not simply focusing on the technology development, but also providing space for experimentation</p>	<p>Rather than thinking about the development of technologies only, we try to create the space for <i>experimentation and dissemination of technologies in the context where they are inserted so that they can maximize the positive impacts.</i> (BR05)</p>

Name	Description	Example
	<p>and dissemination <i>in context</i> for maximising positive impact</p>	<p>A big reference in the implementation of interventions is <i>the technology readiness</i>; we try to <i>understand the solutions that derive from the territory and how they are set with respect to the technology availability to the citizen</i> (I01)</p>
<p>- Importance of politics</p>	<p>Any reference to how local/international politics or internal politics within the organisation can play a role or influence (R)RI practices</p>	<p>Once you finished, it became <i>a political decision about whether to go ahead or not</i>. And in fact, <i>the political decision at this point has not been to go ahead, because it's too expensive</i>, and for other reasons had nothing to do with the content [of the project]. (IL01)</p> <p>Sometimes we would have discussions with environmental charities, for example, throughout the world because that can be <i>very influential on political decision-making and then implementation of regulatory decision-making</i>. (GB01)</p>
<p>- Accounting for geographic scale</p>	<p>Text coded to references of differences in or accounting for geographical scales to highlight how local/ area-specific policies might influence/apply to technologies or products that are, in fact, for global use or how local policies are applied to/influenced by larger national, international or even global standards/policies. Rules: This code can include any implications on the difference in scale of policies. It can also include interactions or comparisons between different contexts like the Global North and South.</p>	<p>There is a tendency now not to develop products that are specific for the EU, we develop for other parts of the world and if they happen to be useful for the EU then we might market them here but otherwise we will just say we are working in South America or North America or just somewhere that it's more open and receptive to the sort of products we are trying to sell. (GB01)</p> <p>... the activities are always innovative given a context traditionally dominated by the unequal relationship of the north and south, or between the rest of Brazil versus the Amazon (BR03)</p> <p>The very question of the continental dimension of Brazil in view of the decision of the 1988 Constitution that established the free and unique health system at the national level brought different challenges for us. First, <i>if we consider the difference between the Brazilian reality and the reality of the countries where this universal health model was already being implemented</i>. They were countries with an economic situation and a social moment in terms of much more advanced equity. The welfare state, like the English model. In this...we still have to face the structural challenges that accompany this decision. (BR06)</p>
<p>Evaluation</p>	<p>Any reference to undertaking research and innovation through evaluation processes. This can include formative evaluation (such as assessing risk, feasibility, forecasting, etc); implementation evaluation (such as assessing/ensuring applicability, implementation, etc); and impact evaluation. Rule: Evaluation here is understood as the more in terms of the formal procedures and established methods used, e.g. quality testing, forecasting, risk assessment, impact assessment, etc.</p>	<p>They are also part of the evaluation at the end of project and before granting process. When researcher submit a proposal, we invite them to register in the evaluation panels in "STDF domain experts (EG02)</p> <p><i>We do risk analysis</i>. Everything has to be risk assessed practically... if this thing is done <i>what are the risks, what are the implications and all that</i>. So, risk metrics and to analyse the risk implications. (ROU02)</p> <p>We meet with each university or research center, we put our plan from the beginning of the year and then we implement the plan and <i>we have this kind of interim evaluation</i> and then have meeting to evaluate what's going on. (EG03)</p>

Name	Description	Example
	<p>This code will include references to evaluation <u>FOR AND AT any stage</u> of the R&I process. It will NOT be confined to anticipatory (future-oriented) processes only.</p>	<p>We use strategic planning documents to <i>plan for the future like five-year strategy</i>. We look at that and we look at future based kind of documents like the premier plans, and <i>we look at the trends within the factor</i>. (ZA06)</p> <p>We've done <i>research on the performance of those improved insulation technologies and how well they work, and what changes to the supply chain we might need to take to...</i> We might need to make to ensure that those technologies can be rolled out a large scale across the UK. (GB08)</p>
- Importance of feedback	<p>Any reference to need for improved feedback mechanisms for improved forecasting and evaluation. Rule: This can include references to both formative and summative feedback.</p>	<p>Very rarely do <i>we get the feedback</i>, which makes it a lot harder to evaluate what we did good, and what we did bad. (SRB04)</p> <p><i>Attention is given to feedback regarding the policies implementation. This monitoring on interventions allows having, quite concretely, the level of perception of the added value the intervention can produce.</i> (I01)</p>
R&I capacity building	<p>Any reference to building capacity for research and innovation as a means of improving responsibility. This can be in terms of local development, contextual development, etc.</p>	<p>...actually, the problem is not in the polices rather <i>research centres themselves need more capacity building programs</i> to satisfy their needs and satisfy the need of the society and the country. (EG03)</p> <p>They've also empowered individuals, empowered organizations, but also without taking credit... it's more like an indirect impact... It's more about strengthening the work and strengthening different institutions that are moving around the work. (IND04)</p> <p>What we were looking for then was to try to <i>generate local capacity development in the universities of xxx</i> (ROU02)</p>
Participation in upstream R&I	<p>Any references to participation of various stakeholder types in the research and innovation process and how that helps to improve and enhance (R)RI; whether it is citizen participation, or participation of diverse groups (females, minorities, etc)</p>	<p><i>We believe that citizens should have a central role in decision-making</i> (I04)</p> <p>we seek to <i>ensure that all parties involved are listened to very carefully and actively participate in all decisions taken</i>. (BR05)</p> <p>...try to recognize that it is good that the neighbour who is going to be very close to a power station of this type, a generator, <i>his/her opinion is valid as much as the bank that is going to be financing it</i>. (ROU02)</p>
<p>10. Constraints Any reference to actors that constrain/inhibit RRI (This section will include references to any enablers of RRI from the entire interview text and so will include high-level codes that cut across all or most of the RRI themes on which the interview questions are bases)</p>		
Time frames and time constraints	<p>Any reference for the need to determine proper time-frames- short-term versus long-term goals for (R)RI or reference to constraints in time that hinder RRI practices, whether in terms of prioritisation of short-term goals, time lags, time-dependent funding of research projects, etc</p>	<p>Some of the things we develop take such a long time to get to market sometimes <i>the market can change completely by the time you get it there</i>. Perhaps you can try to summarize it best in trying to get some foresight; what is the situation going to be like in five- or 10-years' time when we actually want to put this potential product through the regulatory approvals or launch it onto the market. (GB01)</p>

Name	Description	Example
		<p><i>It takes at least eight years to create a portfolio of technologies and solutions for long-term situations that allow us to meet without the need to seek capital. (BR05)</i></p> <p>In the future, we aim to have part of the evaluation form focus on the procedures and implications of research on a <i>short time, long term, and the short term expected results. (EG02)</i></p> <p><i>..we can actually think about only the short term consequences of ethics... for example, when I'm talking to the participant or patient, we are telling them that we are getting this sample and things which will help us to develop a very nice test. And that is useful for them. But it is never directly (useful) to them. It's the hope that that kind of test will be available...so sometimes even though it is an informed consent and feedback, but our long-term deliverable and all those things are not sure. (IND01)</i></p>
Financial constraints and consideration	Any reference to constraints in financial investment that hinder/constrain RRI practices.	<p>However, this product, a still rudimentary prototype, needed investment to conduct practical experiments, field pilots, and continue research...involvement in the support of 'hard science' is very expensive (BR05)</p> <p>Bulk of research in India is state funded whether it is in universities or national laboratories or, you know, other research institutes. <i>It's all state-funded, private, money is very little. (IND02)</i></p>
Lack of (perceived) interest of general public	Any reference to a disinterest or the lack of interest of the general public in R&I	<p>If I write about or if I try to communicate fundamental research, <i>it will not be of great interest to people. (IND02)</i></p> <p><i>I don't think (the public) really care what we do or who we do it for. As consumers, they are very uninvolved and uncritical, I would say (JPN02)</i></p>
Lack of (perceived) applicability of RRI	Any reference to the lack (or uncertainty) of perceived benefit, applicability or relevance of RRI to the respondents' specific work/organisation	<p>I: how do you look at the future implications? And this is when you develop your work plans</p> <p><i>I don't think that is applicable to the kind of work which we do. As I said, there are two cultures. No, we are not looking at a research project which we'll have long, you know! So, it won't really apply. (IND02)</i></p> <p>I: Moving to ethics, what steps do you take to ensure that the way you do your work does not cause concerns for society?</p> <p><i>I think this is not relevant to us. At xxx we make information available to everyone. That includes scientific materials, educational content and scientific journals. (EG03)</i></p> <p><i>I don't have a lot of experience in actually doing the research at the bench. I don't know how much diversity helps. It may do. I'm just not sure of this science-society-policy interaction. (GB01)</i></p>

<p>Conflicts/tensions between theory and practice</p>	<p>Description</p>	<p>Example</p>
<p>Conflicts/tensions in R&I expectations</p>	<p>Any reference to the tensions and conflicts in RRI due to differences between theory and practice. These can be differences in expectations, goals and outcomes or priorities (This section is based on the inductive analysis of the interviews and will include references to any conflicts and tensions in RRI due to differences in theory and practice. It will include codes from the entire interview text that cut across all or most of the RRI themes on which the interview questions are based)</p> <p>Any reference to conflicts between the motivations and priorities of scientific R&I and those of different stakeholders. Any tensions between what is 'wanted' and what is 'needed'.</p> <p>Any reference to tensions, conflicts or disconnects between: Fundamental and applied research Scientific theory and practice Research and industry/business Research and policy, etc Regulations versus research progress Rules: These can be because of different normative frames or different research priorities and end-goals.</p>	<p>Working with them, with companies, sometimes <i>their strategic plan is not aligned with the call, with expertise that we need for the call</i> [grant], but they know that we could be funded. So, sometimes <i>they try to bring to the front some topics that are within their strategy and that's always a problem for us.</i> (IL02)</p> <p>We are talking about scientists and inventors, not entrepreneurs. For example, also involving patent issues, continuous mobilization of resources...<i>when assuming the role of entrepreneur, the research has to leave its comfort zone and take risks</i> (BR05)</p> <p><i>The rules of academia are getting your papers published in the highest impact journals. The rules of society trying to solve societal problems. And because of the mismatch of the two, if I spend my time trying to solve society's problems, I would not be doing my job as an academic.</i> (IL01)</p> <p>The xxx, sometimes, they can say <i>that it is not a priority</i> for the xxx. Here, we get to point zero, and <i>we have nothing to work at because the priorities are not determined on national level.</i> (HKJD)</p> <p>The regulation is so arduous, even if you have a free choice of methods, is that the best method you choose? But <i>the regulation is often so that it will make you not choose that method and you choose one that's more conventional</i> breeding, you get your actual product it gets to the market quicker and there's nothing much regulation. (GB01)</p> <p>We do have the ability to fund projects involving technical academics with private sector; however, <i>we are not entitled to fund private sector</i>, so the money will go to researcher alone and the research institution. But then, when you have the artefact, what's coming out if you have a patient or idea, something you can market or sell, then <i>you have to hit the wall again on how to market that... Once they have innovation or sellable something that can bring money back then, basically, you kill it by these restrictive regulations.</i> (EG02)</p>
<p>12. Collaboration</p>	<p>Any reference to collaboration and collective working as an enabler of RRI in its various aspects (This section is based on the inductive analysis of the interviews and will include references to any discussion on collaboration. It will include codes from the entire interview text that cut across all or most of the RRI themes on which the interview questions are based)</p>	

Name	Description	Example
<p>Building support networks and strategic alliances</p>	<p>Any reference to opportunities for finding common grounds, building support networks and mutually beneficial relationships, and/or making connections for research and innovation.</p> <p>Rules: This includes references to building relationships and making connections in order to facilitate useful outcomes for research and innovation (e.g. in terms of support for strategic ambitions). This does NOT include simple exchange/transfer of knowledge.</p>	<p>We can try to understand much better what their concerns are, and I think increasingly, trying to identify some common ground. Rather than arguing about what we disagree on, <i>we can find something that we agree on and work on that to build stronger relationships.</i> (GB01)</p> <p>We needed for that project a lot of different expertise... I like these <i>large collaborations</i>, so I even have them without funding, with the same Italian researcher, and the researcher that approached me from Canada, and I did research with his group, and they added friends from USA and Poland, and I brought my friends from Italy and then we need Psychology so he added someone from Canada, and he also added someone from Ireland. So, <i>we are all working in the very large collaboration.</i> (IL02)</p>
<p>- “Ecosystem of support”</p>	<p>Invivo coding- Any reference to developing an ‘ecosystem of support’ (i.e. an interactive and integrative system of diverse stakeholders that form a complex system of support) through collaboration; e.g. through effective marketing and technology development.</p>	<p>...many of these innovations ended up not being applied, being on the shelves or were objects of publications that were pending...<i>a team that provided an ecosystem of support</i> so that they arrived at the market effectively (BR05)</p> <p>It’s again that accessibility of information, our transparency as an organization, and the collaboration with the other organizations in the area of technology, because I think that <i>together, we create some sort of ecosystem</i>, and it’s on us, because we are still outside of the reach of the state (SRB02)</p>
<p>Actor mapping</p>	<p>Any reference to mapping all relevant stakeholders for engagement and/or collaboration</p>	<p>It is basically to <i>try to have the actor map as clear as possible</i>... It is the day-to-day work. It is a lot of exchange and good, after building let’s say, collectively in that way <i>everyone in their role, that is, clearly, we cannot do it alone.</i> (ROU02)</p>
<p>Integration of different domains and stakeholders</p>	<p>Any reference to the need for better integration and collaboration between different domains and stakeholders (both cross-disciplinary or otherwise) or involvement/participation at different phases of R&I.</p>	<p>Until recently, every sector has looked at itself and at its own interests without seeking a more systemic approach. Even in the area of research, perhaps, there has been a hyper-specialization and a large focus that evidently produces a limitation of interest. If there is little interest and our associates are not sensitive to a new approach then we, as a federation, also tend to do less. However, <i>the policy lines of Horizon 2020 and, even more, of the Horizon Europe tend to widen and transversal actions. This also affects knowledge in the various sectors, making the habit of hyper-focus less strong.</i> (I03)</p> <p>We invited more than 80 people to participate in the first meeting, which would be a public consultation. We understand that <i>in order to draw the issues we need to invite different actors.</i> Then, we invite the State Health Secretariat, the scientific academy, grassroots civil society organizations, among others. At xxx, we understand that <i>only in this way can we really identify what is feasible to implement, which, in fact, is a project that can be executed, can be approved, and will bring effective results.</i> (BR03)</p>
<p>(R)RI frameworks for new cross-disciplinary research</p>	<p>Any reference to the need for new R&I policies (within any theme) that address new forms of collaboration and cross-disciplinary research work</p>	<p>We are now crossing the border with biological sciences, artificial intelligence and with gene-editing; that’s engineering and that’s biology. So, this is a new area and we are walking into new territory. I am talking as an engineer, not as xxx, we do need now an ethical framework. (EG02)</p>

Name	Description	Example
		<p>They set up a facebook group, and the patients respond... they aren't doing anything illegal, but they don't have the certificate for it...I told them what they should do on their website. I also advised them that when they give out their data, they should give out a consent form that they know what research will be done. So, <i>I kind of educated the people in industry of how they should be protecting the data according to the regulations of xxx... there are sectors that I think are less aware of patient's privacy and should be made more aware (IL02)</i></p>
<p>Difficulties in collaboration and engagement</p>	<p>Any reference to perceived difficulties in bringing about collaboration e.g. in terms of trust, restrictions in communication of any sort between different stakeholder types, etc</p> <p>Rules: This includes difficulties faced in any form of collaborative work in R&I; where different stakeholders are trying to collaborate and forming partnerships, as opposed to difficulties faced because of forces/stakeholders outside of the collaboration</p>	<p>We often published joint publications with staff from xxx authorities. Now its their policy not to do that because <i>they received complaints from NGOs that the authorities are getting too close to the industry.</i> So, it's actually that <i>we are finding it increasingly difficult to have discussions that I think are more or less essential, really.</i> (GB01)</p> <p>I do not like using the word hamper, I think every institution has a different bureaucratic process. While NGOs are extremely fast, <i>we cannot compare the NGO process with a bureaucratic process within government or universities. I believe we have to respect the institutional procedures of each partner, even though I acknowledge that this may be detrimental to the project.</i> (BR03)</p>

No.	Participant	Country	Gender	Stakeholder type	Domain
1	BR03a	Brazil	Male	Civil society organisation Policy bodies	Bioeconomy Energy
	BR03b	Brazil	Female and/or other	Civil society organisation Policy bodies	Bioeconomy Energy
2	BR05	Brazil	Male	Civil society organisation Research funding organisation	Bioeconomy Waste management Energy
3	BR06	Brazil	Male	Research organisation Research funding organisation	ICT
4	EG02	Egypt	Male	Research funding organisation	All
5	EG03	Egypt	Female and/or other	Policy bodies	ICT
6	EG10	Egypt	Male	Industry and business	Waste management
7	GB01	UK	Male	Industry and business	Bioeconomy
8	GB03	UK	Female and/or other	Industry and business	ICT
9	GB08	UK	Male	Civil society organisation	Energy
10	HKJ01	Jordan	Female and/or other	Research organisation	Bioeconomy
11	HKJ02	Jordan	Male	Research organisation	Energy
12	HKJ04	Jordan	Female and/or other	Civil society organisation	Waste management
13	IL01	Israel	Male	Research organisation	Waste management
14	IL02	Israel	Female and/or other	Research organisation	ICT
				Research organisation Industry and business	Energy ICT
15	IL04	Israel	Male	Research organisation Industry and business	Energy ICT
16	IND01	India	Male	Research organisation	Bioeconomy
17	IND02	India	Male	Policy bodies	ICT
18	IND04	India	Female and/or other	Research organisation	Waste management
19	I01	Italy	Male	Civil society organisation	ICT
20	I03	Italy	Male	Industry and business	Energy ICT
				Industry and business	Bioeconomy ICT
21	I04	Italy	Female and/or other	Industry and business Research organisation Research funding organisation	ICT
22	J01a	Japan	Male	Research organisation Research funding organisation	ICT
	J01b	Japan	Female and/or other	Research organisation Research funding organisation	ICT
22	J01c	Japan	Female and/or other	Research organisation Research funding organisation	ICT

		Japan	Male	Research organisation	Bioeconomy
		Uruguay	Male	Policy bodies	Energy
25	ROU05	Uruguay	Female and/or other	Policy bodies	All
26	SRB02	Serbia	Female and/or other	Civil society organisation	ICT
27	SRB04	Serbia	Female and/or other	Industry and business	Bioeconomy Waste management
28	SRB07	Serbia	Male	Policy bodies	Bioeconomy
29	ZA01	South Africa	Male	Research organisation Civil society organisation	Energy Waste management
30	ZA06	South Africa	Male	Research funding organisation Policy bodies	All